

Neutrosophic α gs Continuity And Neutrosophic α gs Irresolute Maps

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Abstract. Neutrosophic Continuity functions very first introduced by A.A.Salama et.al.Aim of this present paper is, we introduce and investigate new kind of Neutrosophic continuity is called Neutrosophic α gs Continuity maps in Neutrosophic topological spaces and also discussed about some properties and characterization of Neutrosophic α gs Irresolute Maps.

Keywords: Neutrosophic α -closed sets, Neutrosophic semi-closed sets, Neutrosophic α gs-closed sets Neutrosophic α gs Continuity maps, Neutrosophic α gs irresolute maps

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic set theory concepts first initiated by F.Smarandache[11] which is Based on K. Atanassov's intuitionistic[6]fuzzy sets & L.A.Zadeh's [20]fuzzy sets. Also it defined by three parameters truth(T), indeterminacy (I),and falsity(F)-membership function. Smarandache's neutrosophic concept have wide range of real time applications for the fields of [1,2,3,4&5] Information Systems, Computer Science, Artificial Intelligence, Applied Mathematics, decision making. Mechanics, Electrical & Electronic, Medicine and Management Science etc.,

A.A.Salama[16] introduced Neutrosophic topological spaces by using Smarandache's Neutrosophic sets. I.Arokiaarani.[7] et.al., introduced Neutrosophic α -closed sets.P. Ishwarya, [13]et.al., introduced and studied Neutrosophic semi-open sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. Neutrosophic continuity functions introduced by A.A.Salama[15]. Neutrosophic α gs-closed set[8] introduced by V.Banu priya&S.Chandrasekar. Aim of this present paper is, we introduce and investigate new kind of Neutrosophic continuity is called Neutrosophic α gs Continuity maps in Neutrosophic topological spaces and also we discussed about properties and characterization Neutrosophic α gs Irresolute Maps

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we introduce the basic definition for Neutrosophic sets and its operations.

Definition 2.1 [11]

Let E be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set λ writing the format is

$$\lambda = \{ \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$$

Where $\eta_\lambda(e)$, $\sigma_\lambda(e)$ and $\gamma_\lambda(e)$ which represents Neutrosophic topological spaces the degree of membership function, indeterminacy and non-membership function respectively of each element $e \in E$ to the set λ .

Remark 2.2 [11]

A Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \{ \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$ can be identified to an ordered triple $\langle \eta_\lambda, \sigma_\lambda, \gamma_\lambda \rangle$ in $]-0,1+[$ on E.

Remark 2.3[11]

Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \{ \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$ our convenient we can write $\lambda = \langle \eta_\lambda, \sigma_\lambda, \gamma_\lambda \rangle$.

Example 2.4 [11]

we must introduce the Neutrosophic set 0_N and 1_N in E as follows:

0_N may be defined as:

$$(0_1) 0_N = \{ \langle e, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(0_2) 0_N = \{ \langle e, 0, 1, 1 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(0_3) 0_N = \{ \langle e, 0, 1, 0 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(0_4) 0_N = \{ \langle e, 0, 0, 0 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

1_N may be defined as:

$$(1_1) 1_N = \{ \langle e, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(1_2) 1_N = \{ \langle e, 1, 0, 1 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(1_3) 1_N = \{ \langle e, 1, 1, 0 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$(1_4) 1_N = \{ \langle e, 1, 1, 1 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

Definition 2.5 [11]

Let $\lambda = \langle \eta_\lambda, \sigma_\lambda, \gamma_\lambda \rangle$ be a Neutrosophic set on E, then λ^C defined as $\lambda^C = \{ \langle e, \gamma_\lambda(e), 1 - \sigma_\lambda(e), \eta_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$

Definition 2.6 [11]

Let E be a non-empty set, and Neutrosophic sets λ and μ in the form

$$\lambda = \{ \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \} \text{ and}$$

$$\mu = \{ \langle e, \eta_\mu(e), \sigma_\mu(e), \gamma_\mu(e) \rangle : e \in E \}.$$

Then we consider definition for subsets ($\lambda \subseteq \mu$).

$\lambda \subseteq \mu$ defined as: $\lambda \subseteq \mu \Leftrightarrow \eta_\lambda(e) \leq \eta_\mu(e), \sigma_\lambda(e) \leq \sigma_\mu(e)$ and $\gamma_\lambda(e) \geq \gamma_\mu(e)$ for all $e \in E$

Proposition 2.7 [11]

For any Neutrosophic set λ , then the following condition are holds:

$$(i) 0_N \subseteq \lambda, 0_N \subseteq 0_N$$

$$(ii) \lambda \subseteq 1_N, 1_N \subseteq 1_N$$

Definition 2.8 [11]

Let E be a non-empty set, and $\lambda = \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle$, $\mu = \langle e, \eta_\mu(e), \sigma_\mu(e), \gamma_\mu(e) \rangle$ be two Neutrosophic sets. Then

$$(i) \lambda \cap \mu \text{ defined as } : \lambda \cap \mu = \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e) \wedge \eta_\mu(e), \sigma_\lambda(e) \wedge \sigma_\mu(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \vee \gamma_\mu(e) \rangle$$

$$(ii) \lambda \cup \mu \text{ defined as } : \lambda \cup \mu = \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e) \vee \eta_\mu(e), \sigma_\lambda(e) \vee \sigma_\mu(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \wedge \gamma_\mu(e) \rangle$$

Proposition 2.9 [11]

For all λ and μ are two Neutrosophic sets then the following condition are true:

$$(i) (\lambda \cap \mu)^C = \lambda^C \cup \mu^C$$

$$(ii) (\lambda \cup \mu)^C = \lambda^C \cap \mu^C.$$

Definition 2.10 [16]

A Neutrosophic topology is a non-empty set E is a family τ_N of Neutrosophic subsets in E satisfying the following axioms:

$$(i) 0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N,$$

$$(ii) G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N \text{ for any } G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N,$$

$$(iii) \cup G_i \in \tau_N \text{ for any family } \{G_i \mid i \in J\} \subseteq \tau_N.$$

the pair (E, τ_N) is called a Neutrosophic topological space.

The element Neutrosophic topological spaces of τ_N are called Neutrosophic open sets.

A Neutrosophic set λ is closed if and only if λ^C is Neutrosophic open.

Example 2.11[16]

Let $E = \{e\}$ and

$$A_1 = \{ \langle e, .6, .6, .5 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$A_2 = \{ \langle e, .5, .7, .9 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$A_3 = \{ \langle e, .6, .7, .5 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

$$A_4 = \{ \langle e, .5, .6, .9 \rangle : e \in E \}$$

Then the family $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4\}$ is called a Neutrosophic topological space on E.

Definition 2.12[16]

Let (E, τ_N) be Neutrosophic topological spaces and $\lambda = \{ \langle e, \eta_\lambda(e), \sigma_\lambda(e), \gamma_\lambda(e) \rangle : e \in E \}$ be a Neutrosophic set in E.

Then the Neutrosophic closure and Neutrosophic interior of λ are defined by

$$\text{Neu-cl}(\lambda) = \cap \{D : D \text{ is a Neutrosophic closed set in } E \text{ and } \lambda \subseteq D\}$$

$$\text{Neu-int}(\lambda) = \cup \{C : C \text{ is a Neutrosophic open set in } E \text{ and } C \subseteq \lambda\}.$$

Definition 2.13

Let (E, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then λ is called

$$(i) \text{ Neutrosophic regular Closed set [7] (Neu-RCS in short) if } \lambda = \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Int}(\lambda)),$$

$$(ii) \text{ Neutrosophic } \alpha\text{-Closed set [7] (Neu-}\alpha\text{CS in short) if } \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))) \subseteq \lambda,$$

$$(iii) \text{ Neutrosophic semi Closed set [13] (Neu-SCS in short) if } \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)) \subseteq \lambda,$$

$$(iv) \text{ Neutrosophic pre Closed set [18] (Neu-PCS in short) if } \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Int}(\lambda)) \subseteq \lambda,$$

Definition 2.14

Let (E, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then λ is called

$$(i). \text{ Neutrosophic regular open set [7] (Neu-ROS in short) if } \lambda = \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)),$$

$$(ii). \text{ Neutrosophic } \alpha\text{-open set [7] (Neu-}\alpha\text{OS in short) if } \lambda \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Int}(\lambda))),$$

$$(iii). \text{ Neutrosophic semi open set [13] (Neu-SOS in short) if } \lambda \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-Int}(\lambda)),$$

$$(iv). \text{ Neutrosophic pre open set [18] (Neu-POS in short) if } \lambda \subseteq \text{Neu-Int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)),$$

Definition 2.15

Let (E, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then λ is called

$$(i). \text{ Neutrosophic generalized closed set [9] (Neu-GCS in short) if } \text{Neu-cl}(\lambda) \subseteq U \text{ whenever } \lambda \subseteq U \text{ and } U \text{ is a Neu-}$$

- OS in E ,
- (ii).Neutrosophic generalized semi closed set[17] (Neu-GSCS in short) if $\text{Neu-scl}(\lambda) \subseteq U$ Whenever $\lambda \subseteq U$ and U is a Neu-OS in E ,
- (iii).Neutrosophic α generalized closed set [14](Neu- α GCS in short) if $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{cl}(\lambda) \subseteq U$ whenever $\lambda \subseteq U$ and U is a Neu-OS in E ,
- (iv).Neutrosophic generalized alpha closed set [10] (Neu-G α CS in short) if $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{cl}(\lambda) \subseteq U$ whenever $\lambda \subseteq U$ and U is a Neu- α OS in E .

The complements of the above mentioned Neutrosophic closed sets are called their respective Neutrosophic open sets.

Definition 2.16 [8]

Let (E, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topological space. Then λ is called Neutrosophic α generalized Semi closed set (Neu- α GSCS in short) if $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{cl}(\lambda) \subseteq U$ whenever $\lambda \subseteq U$ and U is a Neu-SOS in E

The complements of Neutrosophic α GS closed sets is called Neutrosophic α GS open sets.

3. Neutrosophic α GS-Continuity maps

In this section we Introduce Neutrosophic α -generalized semi continuity maps and study some of its properties.

Definition 3.1.

A maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ is called a Neutrosophic α -generalized semi continuity(Neu- α GS continuity in short) $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in (E_1, τ_N) for every Neu-CS μ of (E_2, σ_N)

Example 3.2.

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.7, .5, .8), (.5, .5, .4) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (1, .5, .9), (.2, .5, .3) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively.

Define a maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Then f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Theorem 3.3.

Every Neu-continuity maps is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Proof.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu-continuity maps. Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Since f is a Neu-continuity maps, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-CS in E_1 . Since every Neu-CS is a Neu- α GSCS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Example 3.4.

Neu- α GS continuity maps is not Neu-continuity maps

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.5, .5, .3), (.7, .5, .8) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.4, .5, .3), (.8, .5, .9) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic sets on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle y, (.3, .5, .4), (.9, .5, .8) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS but not Neu-CS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps but not a Neu-continuity maps.

Theorem 3.5.

Every Neu- α continuity maps is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Proof.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α continuity maps. Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then by hypothesis $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α CS in E_1 . Since every Neu- α CS is a Neu- α GSCS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Example 3.6.

Neu- α GS continuity maps is not Neu- α continuity maps

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.5, .5, .6), (.7, .5, .6) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.3, .5, .9), (.5, .5, .7) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle e_2, (.9, .5, .3), (.7, .5, .5) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS continuity maps.

Remark 3.7.

Neu-G continuity maps and Neu- α GS continuity maps are independent of each other.

Example 3.8.

Neu- α GS continuity maps is not Neu-G continuity maps.

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.5, .5, .6), (.8, .5, .4) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.7, .5, .4), (.9, .5, .3) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Then f is Neu- α GS continuity maps but not Neu-G continuity maps.

Since $\lambda = \langle e_1, (.4, .5, .7), (.3, .5, .9) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda) = \langle e_2, (.4, .5, .7), (.7, .5, .3) \rangle$ is not Neu-GCS in E_1 .

Example 3.9.

Neu-G continuity maps is not Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.6, .5, .4), (.8, .5, .2) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.3, .5, .7), (.1, .5, .9) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Then f is Neu-G continuity maps but not a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Since $\lambda = \langle e_2, (.7, .5, .3), (.9, .5, .1) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda) = \langle e_1, (.7, .5, .3), (.9, .5, .1) \rangle$ is not Neu- α GSCS in E_1 .

Theorem 3.10.

Every Neu- α GS continuity maps is a Neu-GS continuity maps.

Proof.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps. Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then by hypothesis $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since every Neu- α GSCS is a Neu-GSCS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-GS continuity maps.

Example 3.11.

Neu-GS continuity maps is not Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.8, .5, .4), (.9, .5, .2) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.3, .5, .9), (0.1, .5, .9) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle e_2, (.9, .5, .3), (.9, .5, .1) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is Neu-GSCS in E_1 but not Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu-GS continuity maps but not a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Remark 3.12.

Neu-P continuity maps and Neu- α GS continuity maps are independent of each other.

Example 3.13.

Neu-P continuity maps is not Neu- α GS continuity maps Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.3, .5, .7), (.4, .5, .6) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.8, .5, .3), (.9, .5, .2) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle e_2, (.3, .5, .8), (.2, .5, .9) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is Neu-PCS in E_1 but not Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu-P continuity maps but not Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Example 3.14.

Neu- α GS continuity maps is not Neu-P continuity maps

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.4, .5, .8), (.5, .5, .7) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_1, (.5, .5, .7), (.6, .5, .6) \rangle$ and $W = \langle e_2, (.8, .5, .4), (.5, .5, .7) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, V, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, W, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle y, (.4, .5, .8), (.7, .5, .5) \rangle$ is Neu- α GSCS but not Neu-PCS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is Neu- α GSCS in E_1 but not Neu-PCS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps but not Neu-P continuity maps.

Theorem 3.15.

Every Neu- α GS continuity maps is a Neu- α G continuity maps.

Proof.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps. Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Since f is Neu- α GS continuity maps, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since every Neu- α GSCS is a Neu- α GCS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu- α G continuity maps.

Example 3.16.

Neu- α G continuity maps is not Neu- α GS continuity maps

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.1, .5, .7), (.3, .5, .6) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.7, .5, .4), (.6, .5, .5) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle e_2, (.4, .5, .7), (.5, .5, .6) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is Neu- α GCS in E_1 but not Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu- α G continuity maps but not a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Theorem 3.17.

Every Neu- α GS continuity maps is a Neu-G α continuity maps.

Proof.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps. Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Since f is Neu- α GS continuity maps, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since every Neu- α GSCS is a Neu-G α CS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-G α CS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-G α continuity maps.

Example 3.18.

Neu-G α continuity maps is not Neu- α GS continuity maps Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.5, .5, .7), (.3, .5, .9) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.6, .5, .6), (.5, .5, .7) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Since the Neutrosophic set $\lambda = \langle y, (.6, .5, .6), (.7, .5, .5) \rangle$ is Neu-CS in E_2 , $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is Neu-G α CS in E_1 but not Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Therefore f is a Neu-G α continuity maps but not a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Remark 3.19.

We obtain the following diagram from the results we discussed above.

Theorem 3.20.

A maps $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ is Neu- α GS continuity if and only if the inverse image of each Neutrosophic set in E_2 is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 .

Proof.

first part Let λ be a Neutrosophic set in E_2 . This implies λ^c is Neu-CS in E_2 . Since f is Neu- α GS continuity, $f^{-1}(\lambda^c)$ is Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since $f^{-1}(\lambda^c) = (f^{-1}(\lambda))^c$, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 .

Converse part Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then λ^c is a Neutrosophic set in E_2 . By hypothesis $f^{-1}(\lambda^c)$ is Neu- α GSOS in E_1 . Since $f^{-1}(\lambda^c) = (f^{-1}(\lambda))^c$, $(f^{-1}(\lambda))^c$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 . Therefore $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is Neu- α GS continuity.

Theorem 3.21.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a maps and $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ be a Neu-RCS in E_1 for every Neu-CS λ in E_2 . Then f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 and $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ be a Neu-RCS in E_1 . Since every Neu-RCS is a Neu- α GSCS, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Definition 3.22.

A Neutrosophic Topology (E, τ_N) is said to be an

- (i) Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ (in short Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$) space, if every Neu- α GSCS in E is a Neu-CS in E ,
- (ii) Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$ (in short Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$) space, if every Neu- α GSCS in E is a Neu-GCS in E ,
- (iii) Neu- $\alpha_{gc}U_{1/2}$ (in short Neu- $\alpha_{gc}U_{1/2}$) space, if every Neu- α GSCS in E is a Neu-GSCS in E .

Theorem 3.23.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps, then f is a Neu-continuity maps if E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ space.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 , by hypothesis. Since E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-CS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-continuity maps.

Theorem 3.24.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps, then f is a Neu-G continuity maps if E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$ space.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 , by hypothesis. Since E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-GCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-G continuity maps.

Theorem 3.25.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps, then f is a Neu-GS continuity maps if E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gc}U_{1/2}$ space.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 , by hypothesis. Since E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gc}U_{1/2}$, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-GSCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-GS continuity maps.

Theorem 3.26.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS continuity maps and $g:(E_2, \sigma_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ be an Neutrosophic continuity, then $g \circ f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ is a Neu- α GS continuity.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_3 . Then $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-CS in E_2 , by hypothesis. Since f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps, $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(\lambda))$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence $g \circ f$ is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Theorem 3.27.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a maps from Neutrosophic Topology in E_1 into a Neutrosophic Topology E_2 . Then the following conditions set are equivalent if E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ space.

- (i) f is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.
- (ii) if μ is a Neutrosophic set in E_2 then $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 .
- (iii) $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu)) \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(f^{-1}(\mu))))$ for every Neutrosophic set μ in E_2 .

Proof.

(i) \rightarrow (ii): is obviously true.

(ii) \rightarrow (iii): Let μ be any Neutrosophic set in E_2 . Then $\text{Neu-int}(\mu)$ is a Neutrosophic set in E_2 . Then $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu))$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSOS}$ in E_1 . Since E_1 is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{U}_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu))$ is a Neutrosophic set in E_1 . Therefore $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu)) = \text{Neu-int}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu))) \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(f^{-1}(\mu))))$.

(iii) \rightarrow (i) Let μ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then its complement μ^c is a Neutrosophic set in E_2 . By Hypothesis $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu^c)) \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu^c)))))$. This implies that $f^{-1}(\mu^c) \subseteq \text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-int}(\mu^c)))))$. Hence $f^{-1}(\mu^c)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{OS}$ in E_1 . Since every $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{OS}$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSOS}$, $f^{-1}(\mu^c)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSOS}$ in E_1 . Therefore $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 . Hence f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps.

Theorem 3.28.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a maps. Then the following conditions set are equivalent if E_1 is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{U}_{1/2}$ space.

(i) f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps.

(ii) $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 for every Neu-CS λ in E_2 .

(iii) $\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\lambda)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))$ for every Neutrosophic set λ in E_2 .

Proof.

(i) \rightarrow (ii): is obviously true.

(ii) \rightarrow (iii): Let λ be a Neutrosophic set in E_2 . Then $\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-CS in E_2 . By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 . Since E_1 is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{U}_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))$ is a Neu-CS in E_1 . Therefore $\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))) = f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))$. Now $\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\lambda)))) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda))$.

(iii) \rightarrow (i): Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . By hypothesis $\text{Neu-Cl}(\text{Neu-int}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\lambda)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\lambda)) = f^{-1}(\lambda)$. This implies $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{CS}$ in E_1 and hence it is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 . Therefore f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps.

Definition 3.29.

Let (E, τ_N) be a Neutrosophic topology. The Neutrosophic alpha generalized semi closure ($\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda)$ in short) for any Neutrosophic set λ is Defined as follows. $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda) = \bigcap \{ K \mid K \text{ is a } \text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS} \text{ in } E_1 \text{ and } \lambda \subseteq K \}$. If λ is $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$, then $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda) = \lambda$.

Theorem 3.30.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps. Then the following conditions set are hold.

(i) $f(\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f(\lambda))$, for every Neutrosophic set λ in E_1 .

(ii) $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$, for every Neutrosophic set μ in E_2 .

Proof.

(i) Since $\text{Neu-Cl}(f(\lambda))$ is a Neu-CS in E_2 and f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f(\lambda)))$ is $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 . That is $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(f(\lambda)))$. Therefore $f(\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(\lambda)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f(\lambda))$, for every Neutrosophic set λ in E_1 .

(ii) Replacing λ by $f^{-1}(\mu)$ in (i) we get $f(\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(f^{-1}(\mu))) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f(f^{-1}(\mu))) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)$. Hence $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$, for every Neutrosophic set μ in E_2 .

4. Neutrosophic α -Generalized Semi Irresolute Maps

In this section we Introduce Neutrosophic α -generalized semi irresolute maps and study some of its characterizations.

Definition 4.1.

A maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ is called a Neutrosophic alpha-generalized semi irresolute ($\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute) maps if $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in (E_1, τ_N) for every $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ λ of (E_2, σ_N)

Theorem 4.2.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute, then f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps.

Proof.

Let f be a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute maps. Let λ be any Neu-CS in E_2 . Since every Neu-CS is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$, λ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_2 . By hypothesis $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_2 . Hence f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps.

Example 4.3.

$\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity maps is not $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute maps.

Let $E_1 = \{a_1, a_2\}$, $E_2 = \{b_1, b_2\}$, $U = \langle e_1, (.4, .5, .7), (.5, .5, .6) \rangle$ and $V = \langle e_2, (.8, .5, .3), (.4, .6, .7) \rangle$. Then $\tau_N = \{0_N, U, 1_N\}$ and $\sigma_N = \{0_N, V, 1_N\}$ are Neutrosophic Topologies on E_1 and E_2 respectively. Define a maps $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ by $f(a_1) = b_1$ and $f(a_2) = b_2$. Then f is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ continuity. We have $\mu = \langle e_2, (.2, .5, .9), (.6, .5, .5) \rangle$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_2 but $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is not a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 . Therefore f is not a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute maps.

Theorem 4.4.

Let $f: (E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GS}$ irresolute, then f is a Neutrosophic irresolute maps if E_1 is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{U}_{1/2}$ space.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_2 . Then λ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_2 . Therefore $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{GSCS}$ in E_1 , by hypothesis. Since E_1 is a $\text{Neu-}\alpha\text{U}_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-CS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neutrosophic irresolute maps.

Theorem 4.5.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ and $g:(E_2, \sigma_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ be Neu- α GS irresolute maps, then $g \circ f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ is a Neu- α GS irresolute maps.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu- α GSCS in E_3 . Then $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . Since f is a Neu- α GS irresolute maps. $f^{-1}((g^{-1}(\lambda)))$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence $g \circ f$ is a Neu- α GS irresolute maps.

Theorem 4.6.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS irresolute and $g:(E_2, \sigma_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ be Neu- α GS continuity maps, then $g \circ f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_3, \rho_N)$ is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu-CS in E_3 . Then $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . Since f is a Neu- α GS irresolute, $f^{-1}((g^{-1}(\lambda)))$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Hence $g \circ f$ is a Neu- α GS continuity maps.

Theorem 4.7.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a Neu- α GS irresolute, then f is a Neu-G irresolute maps if E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$ space.

Proof.

Let λ be a Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . By hypothesis, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since E_1 is a Neu- $\alpha_{gb}U_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(\lambda)$ is a Neu-GCS in E_1 . Hence f is a Neu-G irresolute maps.

Theorem 4.8.

Let $f:(E_1, \tau_N) \rightarrow (E_2, \sigma_N)$ be a maps from a Neutrosophic Topology E_1 Into a Neutrosophic Topology E_2 . Then the following conditions set are equivalent if E_1 and E_2 are Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ spaces.

- (i) f is a Neu- α GS irresolute maps.
- (ii) $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 for each Neu- α GSOS μ in E_2 .
- (iii) $\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$ for each Neutrosophic set μ of E_2 .

Proof.

(i) \rightarrow (ii) : Let μ be any Neu- α GSOS in E_2 . Then μ^c is a Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . Since f is Neu- α GS irresolute, $f^{-1}(\mu^c)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . But $f^{-1}(\mu^c) = (f^{-1}(\mu))^c$. Therefore $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 .

(ii) \rightarrow (iii) : Let μ be any Neutrosophic set in E_2 and $\mu \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)$. Then $f^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$. Since $\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)$ is a Neu-CS in E_2 , $\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . Therefore $(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))^c$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_2 . By hypothesis, $f^{-1}((\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))^c)$ is a Neu- α GSOS in E_1 . Since $f^{-1}((\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))^c) = (f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)))^c$, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$ is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Since E_1 is Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ space, $f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$ is a Neu-CS in E_1 . Hence $\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))) = f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$. That is $\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu))$.

(iii) \rightarrow (i) : Let μ be any Neu- α GSCS in E_2 . Since E_2 is Neu- $\alpha_{ga}U_{1/2}$ space, μ is a Neu-CS in E_2 and $\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu) = \mu$. Hence $f^{-1}(\mu) = f^{-1}(\text{Neu-Cl}(\mu)) \supseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu))$. But clearly $f^{-1}(\mu) \subseteq \text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu))$. Therefore $\text{Neu-Cl}(f^{-1}(\mu)) = f^{-1}(\mu)$. This implies $f^{-1}(\mu)$ is a Neu-CS and hence it is a Neu- α GSCS in E_1 . Thus f is a Neu- α GS irresolute maps.

Conclusion

In this research paper using Neu- α GSCS (Neutrosophic α gs-closed sets) we are defined Neu- α GS continuity maps and analyzed its properties. After that we were compared already existing Neutrosophic continuity maps to Neu- α GSCS continuity maps. Furthermore we were extended to this maps to Neu- α GS irresolute maps, Finally This concepts can be extended to future Research for some mathematical applications.

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Received: January 7, 2019. Accepted: May 20, 2019